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OLENA FEDYUK

Networks that Catch

A Collision of 'Old' and 'New' Migrations in the Context of the War in Ukraine

I haven't spoken to Nadia since 2015. In April 2022, she called my Hungarian number from Naples, where she had worked as a caregiver for over 15 years. She said that she needed to talk to someone, to help her decide what to do. She said her head was so full of confusing information, and that she felt incredible pressure to make the right choice for everyone. Since the beginning of the full-scale war in February 2022, Nadia had managed to bring over from Kyiv her mother, who was a cancer patient, her daughter – a 35-year-old lawyer from the Kyiv area – and her two teenage grandchildren. They all now lived with Nadia in Italy, all surviving on her income alone. Her mother needed surgery. Her daughter was thinking about going to earn money elsewhere, alone, leaving her two teenagers with Nadia. And then, there was Nadia's own job to attend to.

As in Nadia's case, the war has pushed much of the financial, emotional and social responsibilities of support to the networks well beyond Ukrainian borders. Much of the costs of new mobility, precipitated by the crisis, became individualised and redistributed further along already asymmetric transnational networks of care. Most people I met, while volunteering at a train station in March 2022 in Budapest, were fleeing the war to a specific destination: Poland, Spain, Italy, Germany, France. 'No sandwiches please, can you help us buy a ticket?' was the phrase that I translated the most often. Many had to make uneasy choices between two or three possible destinations: there could be a relative in one country, who might be too demanding in terms of familial obligations, then a friend in another country, who could provide greater moral support but had no clear housing options, or a former colleague in a third place. Potential wages, rent prices, social support, trust and childhood dreams of the Western 'dolce

vita – all these gained prominence in minds of people struggling with the chaos of their current situations, trying to ‘do the right thing’ for the entire family in the context of rapidly dwindling resources. Nevertheless, in most cases, everyone had someone abroad to help them make the first step.

While EU states provided the opening for this new mobility, it is old networks of labour migration that bore the weight of managing this crisis. The UNHCR (2022) indicates that, since February 2022, over eight million people have crossed the border from Ukraine. Looking at their countries of destination reveals that movement of people to a large extent mirrored already established labour migration routes. Because the activation of these networks is so situational and personalised, it seems difficult to draw any collective lessons from it. And yet, it is very important to understand the dynamic connection between ‘old’ and ‘new’ mobilities, in particular, the intensification of and shift in care responsibilities in established networks and a new intersectionality of vulnerabilities. As the editorial of this issue argues, the public have a responsibility to not only inform themselves but to generate reflexive public knowledge about this war (also see Kulick 2022). Many labour migrants saw their obligations multiply, as they needed to figure out safe ways to evacuate their families, make arrangements of care for those (often elderly) people who stayed, and save the remaining property and material assets of entire families, even pets. In their remaining free time, many also volunteer, protest the war and donate to Ukraine. In these times, the informal networks of material, social and moral support built over the last 30 years of extensive Ukrainian labour migration not only became the networks that caught and supported those fleeing the war. In many places, these same networks applied political pressure that helped shape local and national responses of EU states to the war in Ukraine. Not to mention their votes, which helped Ukraine win Eurovision . . .

And yet, after assisting their families to flee the war and reuniting with them in destination countries, many migrants found their jobs and ability to earn and provide for their families compromised. For instance, many Ukrainians who came to work in Hungary before the war stayed in workers’ dormitory accommodation, where life regimes are subjected to the rhythms of production and give opportunity to maximise income in order to support distant families. Reuniting with family members and dependants revealed how much these housing options function as extensions of production regimes, shaping migrants into a particular working subject (Schling 2017), and how they are incompatible with family life and work–life balance. Furthermore, night work shifts and extra hours that previously guaranteed relatively good income through the accumulation of overtime bonuses also became unsustainable with new family life rhythms, thus reducing their income below a subsistence level. Similarly, people like Nadia, who provide care and domestic services so that other families can have more quality time, as well as more opportunities for work and personal growth, found it hard to reconcile full-time domestic sector jobs with care for their own families. Paradoxically, the arrival of families and dependants into the established migration networks brought to light the true cost of labour migration regimes. These jobs are made sustainable mostly due to the sacrifice of any semblance of a work–life balance among labour migrants. This has resulted in an instrumentalised turnover of people, bringing in those who can entrust highly gendered tasks of care along their family

networks and are thus able to separate the time and space of work from the time and space of 'life' back at home.

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EMMA RIMPILÄINEN

Housing Preferences of Temporary Protection Seekers in Finland

Since February 2022, over 50,000 people from Ukraine have arrived in Finland to seek temporary protection (Finnish Immigration Service 2023). Unlike in the case of asylum seekers from Africa, Asia or the Middle East, the majority of newcomers from Ukraine have been housed in private accommodation with friends, relatives or even previously unfamiliar volunteers rather than in reception centres. According to a survey conducted among displaced Ukrainians in Finland in summer 2022, less than a third of the respondents lived in reception centres (Svynarenko and Koptsuykh 2022). While asylum seekers from other countries are also technically speaking entitled to arrange their own accommodation, in practice the majority of them have been accommodated in reception centres while their applications are processed. Temporary protection applications for Ukrainians are processed very quickly, typically within one or two weeks. Even after receiving a decision, people granted temporary protection have the right to reside in reception centres, but many Ukrainians try to avoid this option if possible.